

THE HISTORICAL, SCIENTIFIC SIGNIFICANCE OF THE WORK "BABURNAMA" IN YOUTH EDUCATION

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Abstract: In this article Zahiriddin Muhammad Babur's greatest work The main topics covered in the work "Boburnoma" are explained from a scientific, historical and educational point of view. The work "Boburnoma" by Zahiriddin Muhammad Babur is noteworthy as a historical literary source because it contains many historical figures, people of literature and art, religious leaders, There is information about branches and princes, beks, amirs and Umars.

Key words: Babur's greatness, "Baburnoma", lyric poet, Indian ethnography and thought, historical figures and works, translation skills, preserved manuscripts, imprinted on the gems of history work

INTRODUCTION

Every nation has great kings, great scientists, great writers and poets who clearly define its historical and cultural national image. Zahiriddin Muhammad Babur also has his place among such great literary children of mankind. In the history of humanity, there are very few people with exceptional personal capabilities, talents and qualities like Baburcha. Babur was a great king, a classic poet, theoretician, literary critic, jurist, linguist, art critic, ethnographer, a scholar of the world of animals and plants, and he was the owner of multifaceted activities and creativity. "Boburnoma" alone is a clear example of his interest in more than twenty fields. Shah Babur is first and foremost a king, the founder of the Babur dynasty. Perhaps, the Baburids will be the dynasty that ruled for the longest years (332) in world history...

LITERATURE AND METHODOLOGY

"Baburnoma" stands out among the works that bear witness to the life of ancient Movarounnahr and its peoples. This work, created by the great lyric poet, Uzbek writer Zahiriddin Muhammad Babur, is a treasure of social-historical, scientific-natural and literary-linguistic information. It describes the events that took place in Central Asia, Afghanistan and India from 1494 to 1530. Babur historical facts He is not satisfied with merely recording, providing chronological information about battles, campaigns, and marches, but he narrates the events in a lively language, paints landscapes, describes nature, ethnographic situations, embodies the era and its characteristics. For this reason, the work is valuable for us not only because of its scientific and historical significance,

but also as one of the bright examples of Uzbek artistic prose. The poet describes his memories simply and fluently in the style of artistic narration. Creates a clear character of dozens of historical figures. He draws pictures of nature scenes, decorates the book with various plots, romantic adventures, and poetic passages. The portraits of the mentioned persons describe their clothing, appearance, character, habits, past, descendants and ancestors one by one. The central character in the work is Babur himself, of course. His heart, full of emotions, comes alive before our eyes. English historian Elfinistan about "Boburnoma" and its author: "His personal feelings are free from any exaggeration or veiling, his style is simple and not heroic, at the same time lively and expressive. He describes the biography of his contemporaries, their faces, customs, aspirations, interests and actions as clearly as reflected in a mirror. In this regard, he writes that "Boburnoma is the only example of a truly historical image in Central Asia." Babur gave rich information about the geography of Central Asia, Khurasan and India, as well as the world of animals and plants. In particular, "Boburnoma" contains valuable facts about Indian ethnography, science, art and culture, and the Tashkent conference of African writers (1958). The famous Indian Indian poet Mulk Raj Anand in his speech to Asia: "This book is our heritage with you. "Boburnoma" is highly valued here, as in Uzbekistan. It was not for nothing. "Baburnoma" is a cultural monument comparable to Alisher Navoi's "Khamsa" due to its coverage of many characteristics of the period, its encyclopedic character and the display of the incomparably rich possibilities of the Uzbek literary language. The fact that the work soon gained fame and was translated into Persian several times already in the 16th century is a proof of our opinion. "Baburnama" was first translated into Persian in 1589 by Abdurahim Khan ibn Bayram Khan Khanon, who was in the service of Shah Akbar's court. The translation was copied in many copies and was widely distributed in Eastern countries under the names "Voqeati Baburii" and "Tarihi Baburshahi". Abdurahim Khan was able to give Babur's unique narrative style in the translation, and the work was accepted as a great innovation in Persian literature and history. Babur's work has a strong influence on the historical memoirs created after him, not only because of the truthful presentation of the covered historical events and the wealth of scientific facts, but also because of his fluent style, simplicity and attractiveness. For example, it can be clearly felt in books such as Gulbadanbegim's Humayunnama and Nizamiddin Hiravi's Tabaqati Akbarshakhi. It should be noted that from the 16th century, other examples of Uzbek literature were also translated into Persian. The advanced intellectuals of the East, seeing that the literature created in Turkic (the old Uzbek language) has a great influence, began to invite scholars to learn this language.

They consider it an important task to translate the wonderful works of Navoi and Babur and make Persians enjoy them. For example, Sultan Muhammad Fakhri Khiroti, who translated "Majolis un-nafais" into Persian in 1521, writes: "Because some respectable and respectable people are not familiar with the Turkish phrase (language), these beautiful words They do not enjoy the waves and the precious gems of this sea of arts. It was a sad state of affairs, and therefore I intended to lift the veil from the face of this dilafroz, who remained in a veil like a Turkish beauty, and to show this beautiful picture created by a miraculous imagination without a veil to the people of virtue and perfection. The decoration of "Boburnima" manuscripts with beautiful paintings also made the translation famous. 104 artists worked in his palace. Translator Abdurahimkhan himself was engaged in painting. Dozens of books were painted in Akbar's palace. Miniatures made from Persian copies of "Baburnoma" are excellent examples of Eastern art. According to the information given by the English orientalist L. King, "Baburnoma" was translated into Persian twice by Muhammadquli and Zayniddin Khawafi. However, the scientist does not say where these translation manuscripts are kept. However, the scientist does not say where these translation manuscripts are kept. Abdurahim Khan's translation is kept in the British Museum and the Fund of Oriental Manuscripts in Moscow. A photocopy is also available in the Alisher Navoi Museum of Literature. Western scholars are first introduced to "Boburnoma" through these Persian copies. Witsen was the first among European orientalists to be interested in "Boburnoma" and translated some parts of it into Dutch. (1705).

DISCUSSION AND RESULT

By the beginning of the 19th century, the work was known to all European scientists. In the global fame of Babur's heritage, the service of British Orientalists is especially great. They take the lead not only in translation and publication of "Boburnoma", but also in research and promotion. On April 12, 1816, William Erskine got up from Bombay and wrote a letter to the inspectors in London, expressing his joy at finding an endless treasure and announcing that he was translating "Baburnoma". A translation by W. Erskine in collaboration with J. Leyden was published in 1826. The translators used the Uzbek and Persian versions of the work as a basis. U. Erskine wrote a big introduction to the book. Introduces Babur and his works to English books: "We rarely meet genius and talented people like Babur among the rulers of Asia. Among the kings of Asia, there is no equal to Babur in terms of the active activity of his mind, his cheerfulness and coolness, despite the tricks of unfaithful fate, his freshness of spirit, his generosity, courage, talent, love for science and art, and his active involvement in

them.” The translation by J. Leyden and W. Erskine was published for the second time in 1921 by Oxford University Press. In this edition, Professor L. Kivt of the University of Dublin writes a foreword and provides information about the editions of "Baburnoma", its copies in the world's manuscript funds, translations, and re-edits the English version. In the scientific essay, which makes up half of the first volume, he extensively covered the history and geography of Movarounnahr and Khurasan, the current situation of Samarkand, Andijan, Oratepa, Kabul and other cities mentioned by Babur. Another feature of this publication is that, in order to ensure the scientific accuracy of the translation, a large number of comments and comments are given in the margins, it is also indicated to whom the poems in the book belong and in which language they were written. Mrs. A. Beveridge, one of the English orientalists, published a facsimile copy of the "Baburnoma" in Hyderabad in 1902. (It was reprinted in London in 1971.)

This publication made the work even more popular. The Russian translation of the work by M. Sale and the Uzbek edition prepared by P. Shamsiyev and S. Mirzayev in 1960 are based on this edition by Mrs. A. Beveridge. "Baburnoma" was abridged and translated into English by P. M. Caldecott. At the end of the 20th century, F. J. Talbot also translated the work and published it with pictures. Also, the famous scientist Rashot Rahman Orat has contributed greatly to the spread of Babur's works in Turkey. Many special monographs have been created in English to study Babur's life and work. These include Len Poole's Babur (Oxford 1899) and Harold Lamb's Babur the Tiger (New York 1961). Especially this book is written in the style of an interesting literary historical essay. This is shown in the internal sections of the book, "Events in the Valley", "Expulsion from Samarkand", "The Sultanate of Kabul", "The Betrayal of Herat", "Babur and his army", "March to India", "Panipat and Kanvand", "Great It can also be known from such titles as the Mongol Empire. H. Lamb widely used Babur's literary heritage as scientific information, mostly referring to "Baburnama" and translating many passages from it. In addition, he traveled on horseback along the paths of Mirza Babur. Thus, this work took the form of a historical novel about Babur. Other British and American scholars who are engaged in the history of the peoples of the East highly appreciate Babur's personal abilities and activities and compare him with the ancient Roman general Julius Caesar. "Baburnoma" was abridged into German by A. Kaiser in 1828 and fully translated into French by P. Curtyl in 1871. Our contemporary, the famous Oriental scholar J. L. Boite Grammon created a new French translation of "Baburnoma". He came to our country several times and got acquainted with the lifestyle and history of the Uzbek people. Grammon also translated Gulbadanbegim's

"Tuzuklari Temur" and "Khumayunnoma" into French. In 1912, Togaymurad Qorluq Khatlani translated it into Persian again. This translation manuscript is kept in the manuscript fund of the Institute of Oriental Studies named after Abu Rayhan Beruni of the Academy of Sciences of the Republic of Uzbekistan.

In 1944-1946, the work was translated into Ottoman Turkish and published in two volumes in Ankara. "Baburnoma" appeared in Russia long ago. Orientalist N. Ilminsky published the work in Kazan in 1857. At the end of the 19th century, some parts of "Baburnoma" were partially presented to Russian readers in the translation of I. Pantusov, S. Polyakov, V. Vyatkin, but the complete Russian translation was not made. This honorable and auspicious work was done by M. Sale, a skilled translator and scientist, and the work was published in Tashkent in 1958. M. Sale worked on the translation for more than ten years, studied the language of the work in depth. Behad managed to give the transcription of many terms, phrases and names, as well as preserve the "heroic style" of Babur's pen. Nevertheless, there are still many uncertainties in M. Sale's translation. Several names in "Baburnoma" are given incorrectly. For example, Akhmad Mirza's lover Qutluq Begim became "Katak Begim", and some words and expressions such as "buckalamun", "muchah" were presented without translation and explanation, so they became incomprehensible to the Russian reader. The poetic passages are given in prose translation, and it is not indicated in which language they were written. Most of the defects in translations and editions are due to the need for a scientific critical text of the work. The existing editions of "boburnoma", even the Uzbek edition, cannot give a complete picture of the work. After all, neither the Russian edition nor the latest Uzbek edition contains a description of the events from 1509 to 1518 and to 1524. In order to eliminate many such ambiguities, it was necessary to compile the most important manuscript copies of "Boburnom" and prepare its scientific text. And finally, this work was carried out by Japanese anthropologists. A critical text of the work was created and published. It can be seen that Mirzo Babur's life and work are being studied in different countries and are becoming a means of international scientific cooperation. This is also a symbol of the great talent and pride of the Uzbek people.

In the work, the events of each year are given separately. All such valuable information and comments are important for history. So, it can be seen that "Baburnima" is an important source for studying the events that took place in these three regions in the last quarter of the 15th century and the first quarter of the 16th century. According to M. Abdullayeva, who conducted research on the work, the names of 1,540 people were mentioned in "Baburnoma", of which 357 are the names of

historical figures from Movarounnahr. The rest are the names of historical figures who lived in different countries in different periods. In the work, Babur does not limit himself to the description of historical events, but also describes in detail the scenery of the circumstances in which the events took place, the appearance and behavior of historical figures, scenes of nature, narrates various adventures, narratives and anecdotes in an attractive artistic style. combines with wisdom, uses artistic methods and language arts. "Description of Alisher Navoi", "Image of Andijan", "Image of Samarkand" taken from "Baburnoma" are vivid examples of this. In "Boburnoma" several hundred historical issues are described, their activities and adventures are described. These are kings, governors, officials, military commanders, religious leaders, soldiers, scientists, poets, artists, representatives of various working classes, etc. These are people with different roles, views and interests, political opinions, behavior, and behavior in society. Babur pays attention to all these aspects when describing the participants of events. He selects only the unique characteristics of people, he writes in full adherence to historical truth, creates extremely believable realistic images. Babur treats historical figures impartially, even his enemies provides unbiased information about them, honestly shows shortcomings in their activities and behavior. The important thing is that it evaluates the historical figures according to their services in the development of the country, development of science, literature and art. - "Baburnoma" has a wide range of opinions about people of science, art and literature. The author of the book provides information about poets and artists such as Alisher Navoi, Jami, Binai, Muhammad Salih, Hilali, Sayfi Bukhari, Mir Husayn Matami, Shayhimbek Sukhaili, Ahmad Hajibek, Begzod, Shah Muzaffar, Ghulam Shadi, Husayn Udi, gives examples of his works. It tells interesting details about their life, activities, behavior.

CONCLUSION

In the work, the place where this event is happening is described before or during the narration of a historical event. As a result, in the eyes of the reader, Mowarounnahr, Khurasan, Afghanistan, India, many provinces, cities and villages in them, land, water and Toru deserts, fields, steppes, orchards, fields, It is reflected in the climate, people, customs, lifestyle, clothing, food, language and dialect of the tribes and peoples. Therefore, in such places Babur is seen not only as a talented poet and writer, but also as a careful and knowledgeable scientist, geographer, ethnographer, naturalist, linguist, and art critic. The artist does not neglect even small details in the depiction of strange places, he paints beautiful realistic paintings embodying the scenery of regions, cities, villages.

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